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ABSTRACT BOOK

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CAN BILE ACIDS BE SAFELY USED AS PHARMACEUTICAL EXCIPIENTS?

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1. INTRODUCTION

The unique structure and physicochemical properties of bile acids have enabled them to be used in the development of drugs, as excipients and drug carriers that could improve, control and localize drug delivery [1].

The availability and low cost of bile acids, along with their simple derivatization procedures, turn them into attractive building blocks for the design of novel pharmaceutical formulations and systems for the delivery of drugs, biomolecules and vaccines [2].

Although bile acids have not been commercialized as excipients in conventional dosage forms such as tablets, they are being investigated as excipients specifically for drug molecules that need permeation enhancers to be readily absorbed. Bile acids in the tablet formulations can be exploited to enhance the release, i.e., dissolution rate of the active substance as well [3].

Hydrophobicity is the main determinant of bile acids toxicity and depends on the number, position and orientation of the hydroxyl groups. Replacement of hydroxyl groups by keto groups in the structure of bile acids makes them more hydrophilic and less toxic and thus suitable for the use as drug excipients [4].

The aim of this study was to analyze the impact of non-toxic bile acids, the most hydrophilic natural bile acid ursodeoxycholic acid (UDCA) and semi-synthetic 12-monoketocholic acid (MKC) on pharmacological activity of antitumor (cytotoxic) drug vorinostat against colon cells.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Materials

Human colon adenocarcinoma HT-29 cells were used to assess the cytotoxicity of vorinostat, alone or in combination with bile acids UDCA and MKC.

2.2. Cytotoxicity assessment

Growth inhibition was evaluated by tetrazolium colorimetric MTT assay. Cells were plated into 96-well microtiter plates in a volume of 90 µl per well, in the complete medium at an optimal seeding density of 5×10^3 cells per well to assure a logarithmic growth rate throughout the assay period. Plates were incubated at 37 °C for 48 h. Three hours before the end of incubation period 5 mg/ml MTT solution was added and plates were further incubated. After removal of MTT and medium, the formazan product was then solubilized in 0.04 M HCl of isopropanol. After a few minutes at room temperature, the plates were read on a spectrophotometer plate reader at 540/690 nm. Growth inhibition was expressed as a percent and calculated according to the formula: $\%C = 1 - (OD_{test}/OD_{control}) \times 100$.

2.3. Determination of interaction type

Multiple drug effects were examined by calculating the combination index (CI) as described by Chou and Talalay, using CompuSyn software [5]. $CI < 1$ is evidence for synergism, whereas $CI > 1$ is evidence of antagonism. The logarithmic value of CI index was used to estimate the type of interaction, with positive values indicating antagonism, and negative synergism.